

Fractional-order functions for solving fractional-order variational problems with boundary conditions

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Abstract

In this paper, a numerical method for solving the fractional-order variational problems (FVPs) with boundary conditions is presented. The fractional derivative in the problem is in the Caputo sense. In the presented method, the given optimization problem reduces to a system of algebraic equations using fractional-order Bernoulli functions and their fractional integration operational matrix. An approximate solution for the FVP is achieved by solving this system. Numerical examples are examined to highlight the significant features of the new technique.

Keywords: Fractional-order Bernoulli functions, Fractional variational problems, Operational matrix, Caputo fractional derivative

Mathematics Subject Classification [2010]: 34A08, 34K28, 35E15

1 Introduction

During last few decades, the topic of fractional calculus has been used strongly in describing many real-life phenomena such as hydrologic, economics, continuum and statistical mechanics, solid mechanics, electro-chemistry, biology, finance [1]-[2]. Therefore, constructing new analytical and numerical approaches for solving different types of fractional differential equations has become a strong topic to be considered. Recently, several numerical methods to solve FDEs have been given, such as Fourier transforms, Laplace transforms, Adomian decomposition method, wavelet method [3]-[4].

In this paper, since fractional-order functions can well reflect the properties of the fractional order differential, we attempt to introduce fractional-order Bernoulli functions to interval $[0, 1]$ and to acquire numerical solution of the fractional variational problems with variable coefficients.

2 Basic definitions

In this section we present some basic definitions needed in the following parts of the paper.

2.1 The fractional derivative and integral

Definition 2.1. The Riemann-Liouville fractional integral operator of order $\nu \geq 0$ is defined as ([5])

$$I^\nu f(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu)} \int_0^t \frac{f(s)}{(t-s)^{1-\nu}} ds, & \nu > 0, t > 0, \\ f(t), & \nu = 0. \end{cases}$$

For the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral we have

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$$I^\nu t^\beta = \frac{\Gamma(\beta+1)}{\Gamma(\beta+\nu+1)} t^{\nu+\beta}, \quad \beta > -1.$$

Definition 2.2. Caputo's fractional derivative of order ν is defined as ([5])

$$D^\nu f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\nu)} \int_0^t \frac{f^{(n)}(s)}{(t-s)^{\nu+1-n}} ds, \quad n-1 < \nu \leq n, \quad n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

For the Caputo derivative we have

$$D^\nu I^\nu f(t) = f(t), \quad I^\nu D^\nu f(t) = f(t) - \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} f^{(i)}(0) \frac{t^i}{i!}.$$

2.2 Fractional-order Bernoulli functions

The fractional-order Bernoulli functions (FBFs) can be defined by introducing the change of variable $t \rightarrow (t-c)^\alpha$ (c is a real constant and $\alpha > 0$) based on the Bernoulli polynomials. Let the FBFs be denoted by $F\beta_m^{\alpha,c}(t)$. The analytic form of $F\beta_m^{\alpha,c}(t)$ of order $m\alpha$, is given by

$$F\beta_m^{\alpha,c}(t) = \sum_{i=0}^m \binom{m}{i} \beta_{m-i} (t-c)^{i\alpha}, \quad 0 \leq t \leq 1. \quad (1)$$

Thus, the first four such functions are

$$F\beta_0^{\alpha,c}(t) = 1,$$

$$F\beta_1^{\alpha,c}(t) = (t-c)^\alpha - \frac{1}{2},$$

$$F\beta_2^{\alpha,c}(t) = (t-c)^{2\alpha} - (t-c)^\alpha + \frac{1}{6},$$

$$F\beta_3^{\alpha,c}(t) = (t-c)^{3\alpha} - \frac{3}{2}(t-c)^{2\alpha} + \frac{1}{2}(t-c)^\alpha.$$

For the fractional-order Bernoulli functions, we have

$$\int_0^1 F\beta_n^{\alpha,c}(t) F\beta_m^{\alpha,c}(t) (t-c)^{\alpha-1} dt = \frac{1}{\alpha} (-1)^{n-1} \frac{m!n!}{(m+n)!} \beta_{m+n}, \quad m, n \geq 1. \quad (2)$$

Also, we let

$$\Phi(t) = [F\beta_0^{\alpha,c}(t), F\beta_1^{\alpha,c}(t), F\beta_2^{\alpha,c}(t), \dots, F\beta_m^{\alpha,c}(t)]^T. \quad (3)$$

2.3 Operational matrix of fractional integration

The Riemann-Liouville fractional integration of the vector $\Phi(t)$ given in Eq. (3) can be expressed by

$$I^\nu \Phi(t) = P^{(\nu,\alpha,c)} \Phi(t), \quad (4)$$

where $P^{(\nu,\alpha,c)}$ is the $(m+1) \times (m+1)$ operational matrix of fractional integration. Using Eq. (10) and the properties of the operator I^ν in Definition 1, for $i = 0, 1, \dots, m$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} I^\nu F\beta_i^{\alpha,c}(t) &= I^\nu \left(\sum_{r=0}^i \binom{i}{r} \beta_{i-r} (t-c)^{r\alpha} \right) = \sum_{r=0}^i \binom{i}{r} \beta_{i-r} I^\nu (t-c)^{r\alpha} \\ &= \sum_{r=0}^i \binom{i}{r} \beta_{i-r} \frac{\Gamma(r\alpha+1)}{\Gamma(r\alpha+1+\nu)} (t-c)^{r\alpha+\nu} = \sum_{r=0}^i b_{i,r}^{(\nu,\alpha)} (t-c)^{r\alpha+\nu}, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where

$$b_{i,r}^{(\nu,\alpha)} = \binom{i}{r} \frac{\Gamma(r\alpha+1)}{\Gamma(r\alpha+1+\nu)} \beta_{i-r}.$$

Assume $(t - c)^{r\alpha + \nu}$ can be expanded in $m + 1$ terms of the fractional-order Bernoulli functions as

$$(t - c)^{r\alpha + \nu} \simeq \sum_{j=0}^m \eta_{r,j}^{(\nu, \alpha, c)} F \beta_j^{\alpha, c}(t). \quad (6)$$

By using Eqs. (5) and (6) for $i = 0, 1, \dots, m$, we get

$$I^\nu F \beta_i^{\alpha, c}(t) \simeq \sum_{r=0}^i b_{i,r}^{(\nu, \alpha)} \sum_{j=0}^m \eta_{r,j}^{(\nu, \alpha, c)} F \beta_j^{\alpha, c}(t) = \sum_{j=0}^m \left(\sum_{r=0}^i \Theta_{i,j,r}^{(\nu, \alpha, c)} \right) F \beta_j^{\alpha, c}(t), \quad (7)$$

where

$$\Theta_{i,j,r}^{(\nu, \alpha, c)} = b_{i,r}^{(\nu, \alpha)} \eta_{r,j}^{(\nu, \alpha, c)}.$$

Eq. (7) can be rewritten as

$$I^\nu F \beta_i^{\alpha, c}(t) \simeq \left[\sum_{r=0}^i \Theta_{i,0,r}^{(\nu, \alpha, c)}, \sum_{r=0}^i \Theta_{i,1,r}^{(\nu, \alpha, c)}, \dots, \sum_{r=0}^i \Theta_{i,m,r}^{(\nu, \alpha, c)} \right] \Phi(t), \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, m. \quad (8)$$

Therefore, we have

$$P^{(\nu, \alpha, c)} = \begin{bmatrix} \Theta_{0,0,0}^{(\nu, \alpha, c)} & \Theta_{0,1,0}^{(\nu, \alpha, c)} & \cdots & \Theta_{0,m,0}^{(\nu, \alpha, c)} \\ \sum_{r=0}^1 \Theta_{1,0,r}^{(\nu, \alpha, c)} & \sum_{r=0}^1 \Theta_{1,1,r}^{(\nu, \alpha, c)} & \cdots & \sum_{r=0}^1 \Theta_{1,m,r}^{(\nu, \alpha, c)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ \sum_{r=0}^m \Theta_{m,0,r}^{(\nu, \alpha, c)} & \sum_{r=0}^m \Theta_{m,1,r}^{(\nu, \alpha, c)} & \cdots & \sum_{r=0}^m \Theta_{m,m,r}^{(\nu, \alpha, c)} \end{bmatrix}.$$

3 Problem statement and approximation method

Consider the FVPs

$$\min(\max) J[y] = \int_0^1 F(t, y(t), D^{\nu_1} y(t), D^{\nu_2} y(t)) dt, \quad 0 < \nu_1 \leq 1, 1 < \nu_2 \leq 2, \quad (9)$$

with the boundary conditions

$$\begin{aligned} y(0) &= y_0, & y'(0) &= y'_0, \\ y(1) &= y_1, & y'(1) &= y'_1, \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

here F is smooth functions of their arguments. First, we approximate $D^{\nu_2} y(t)$, $y(t)$, $D^{\nu_1} y(t)$ as

$$D^{\nu_2} y(t) \simeq C^T \Phi(t), \quad (11)$$

$$y(t) \simeq C^T P^{(\nu_2, \alpha, c)} \Phi(t) + y_0 + t y'_0 \quad (12)$$

$$D^{\nu_1} y(t) \simeq C^T P^{(\nu_2 - \nu_1, \alpha, c)} \Phi(t) + \frac{t^{1 - \nu_1}}{\Gamma(\nu_1)} y'_0, \quad (13)$$

By substituting the approximations (11)-(13) in the performance index (9), we get

$$\min(\max) J[C] = \int_0^1 F(t, C^T P^{(\nu_2, \alpha, c)} \Phi(t) + y_0 + t y'_0, C^T P^{(\nu_2 - \nu_1, \alpha, c)} \Phi(t) + \frac{t^{1 - \nu_1}}{\Gamma(\nu_1)} y'_0, C^T \Phi(t)) dt.$$

The optimal control problem has been reduced to a parameter optimization problem, which can be stated as follows. Find C so that $J[C]$ is minimized (or maximized), subject to the constraint in (10). Let

$$J^*[C, \lambda_1, \lambda_2] = J[C] + (C^T P^{(\nu_2, \alpha, c)} \Phi(1) + y_0 + y'_0 - y_1) \lambda_1 + (C^T P^{(\nu_2 - 1, \alpha, c)} \Phi(1) + y'_0 - y'_1) \lambda_2, \quad (14)$$

where λ_1 and λ_2 represents the unknown constant Lagrange multipliers. Then the necessary conditions for minimum (or maximum) of J^* are given by

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial C} J[C, \lambda_1, \lambda_2] = 0, \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_1} J[C, \lambda_1, \lambda_2] = 0, \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_2} J[C, \lambda_1, \lambda_2] = 0.$$

The above relations can be solved for C , λ_1 and λ_2 using the Newton's iterative method.

4 Illustrative test problems

Example 4.1. Consider the following FVP: Find the extremum of the functional ([6])

$$J[y] = \int_0^1 (D^{\frac{1}{4}}y(t) + D^{\frac{5}{4}}y(t) - g(t))^2 dt, \quad (15)$$

where

$$g(t) = \frac{5\sqrt{\pi}\Gamma(\frac{7}{4})t^{\frac{9}{4}}}{2\Gamma(\frac{3}{4})\Gamma(\frac{13}{4})} + \frac{15\sqrt{\pi}t^{\frac{5}{4}}}{8\Gamma(\frac{9}{4})},$$

under the following boundary conditions

$$\begin{aligned} y(0) &= 0, & y'(0) &= 1, \\ y(1) &= 1, & y'(1) &= \frac{5}{2}, \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

For the above problem there exist $y(t) = \frac{t}{2}$ which satisfies all boundary conditions and $J[y] = 0$. In Table 1, a comparison is made between the values of J obtained by Legendre polynomials by $k = 5, k = 10$ together with the present method at $m = 5, 10, \alpha = \frac{1}{2}, c = 0$. In Table 2, the absolute errors of $y(t)$ by the present method and Ref. [6] are demonstrated. Table 3 shows the estimated values of J for $m = 10$ and different values of α .

Table 1: The comparison of the estimated value of J for Example 1

Ref. [6]		present method	
$k = 5$	$k = 10$	$m = 5$	$m = 10$
2.15×10^{-7}	1.54×10^{-8}	5.94×10^{-9}	7.73×10^{-13}

Table 2: The comparison of the absolute errors of $y(t)$ for Example 1

t	Ref. [6]		present method	
	$k = 5$	$k = 10$	$m = 5$	$m = 10$
0.1	1.75×10^{-5}	2.53×10^{-6}	1.64×10^{-7}	3.67×10^{-9}
0.3	2.91×10^{-5}	7.27×10^{-6}	2.46×10^{-7}	1.10×10^{-9}
0.5	8.30×10^{-6}	7.09×10^{-6}	1.50×10^{-6}	3.74×10^{-9}
0.7	1.09×10^{-5}	6.00×10^{-6}	2.11×10^{-6}	4.41×10^{-10}
0.9	1.01×10^{-5}	9.09×10^{-7}	1.19×10^{-6}	6.39×10^{-9}

Table 3: Comparison of of the estimated value of J with $m = 10$ for different values of α for Example 1

$\alpha = \frac{1}{5}$	$\alpha = \frac{1}{4}$	$\alpha = 1$	$\alpha = 2$
8.53×10^{-10}	4.16×10^{-14}	7.73×10^{-13}	5.11×10^{-5}

Example 4.2. Consider the following FVP: Find the extremum of the functional [7]

$$J[y] = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 \left[\frac{1}{2} (D^\nu y(t))^2 - y(t) \right] dt, \quad 0 < \nu \leq 1, \quad (17)$$

under the following boundary conditions

$$y(0) = y(1) = 0. \quad (18)$$

This functional for $\nu = 1$ represents the total potential for a bar fixed at both ends and subjected to uniform loading, and the exact solution is given by $y(t) = \frac{t}{2}(1 - t)$.

In Fig. 1, we presented the behavior of the numerical solutions of the above problem at $m = 4, \alpha = \nu, c = 0$ for different values of ν and the exact solution. In Fig. 2, we presented the absolute errors of $y(t)$ at $\alpha = \nu = 1$ for different values of $m (m = 5, 10)$.

Figure 1: The behavior of $y(t)$ at $m = 4$ for Example 2.

Figure 2: The absolute errors of $y(t)$ at (a) : $M = 5$, (b) : $M = 10$ for Example 2.

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